

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 2.48

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.269657>

Cite this paper as : Vidhun M, Akshara Shanmughan, Liya Immanual, & Sreelakshmi V G (2017).

AUTOMATIC LOAD SHARING OF TRANSFORMERS USING MICROCONTROLLER, Volume 4,(Issue 1, Jan-2017), pp 57-64. ISSN: 2349 –3607 (Online) , ISSN: 2349 –4824 (Print), <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.269657>

AUTOMATIC LOAD SHARING OF TRANSFORMERS USING MICROCONTROLLER

Vidhun M¹, Akshara Shanmughan², Liya Immanual³, Sreelakshmi V G⁴

¹Assistant Professor, ^{2,3,4}B.Tech Student

Dept. of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, IESCE Chittilappilly PO Thrissur Kerala, India

Abstract:

The transformer is a static device, which converts power from one level to another level. The aim of the project is to protect the transformer under overload condition by load sharing. Due to overload on transformer, the efficiency drops and windings get overheated and may get burnt. Thus by sharing load on transformer, the transformer is protected. This will be done by connecting another transformer in parallel through a micro-controller. The micro controller compares the load on the first transformer with a reference value. When the load exceeds the reference value, the second transformer will share the extra load. Therefore, the two transformer work efficiently and damage is prevented. In this project three modules are used to control the load currents. The first module is a sensing unit, which is used to sense the current of the load and the second module is a control unit. The last module is micro-controller unit and it will read the analogue signal and perform some calculation and finally gives control signal to a relay. A GSM modem is also used to inform the control station about switching. The advantages of the project are transformer protection, uninterrupted power supply, and short circuit protection. When designing low-voltage power system to the supply large load currents, paralleled lower-current modules are often preferred over a single, large power converter for several reasons. These include the efficiency of designing and manufacturing standard modular converters which can be combined in any number necessary to meet a given load requirement and the enhanced reliability gained through redundancy.

KEYWORDS: Capacity, Interruption, Load; System, Transformer, Microcontroller.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

Power travels from the power plant to house through an amazing system called the power distribution grid. For power to be useful in a home or business, it comes off the transmission grid and is stepped-down to the distribution grid. This may happen in several phases. The place where the conversion from "transmission" to "distribution" occurs is in a power substation. It has transformers that step transmission voltages (in the tens or hundreds of thousands of volts range) down to distribution voltages (typically less than 10,000 volts). It has a "bus" that can split the distribution power off in multiple directions. It often has circuit breakers and switches so that the substation can be disconnected from the transmission grid or separate distribution lines can be disconnected from the substation when necessary.

Transformers being one of the most significant equipment in the electric power system, needs protection as a part of the general system protection approach. Moreover the increasing population and their unavoidable demands have lead to an increasing demand on electrical power. With this increased needs, the existing systems have become overloaded. The overloading at the consumer end appears at the transformer terminals which can affect its efficiency and protection systems. Due to overload on the transformer, the efficiency drops and the windings gets over heated and may get burnt. It takes a lot of time to repair and involves a lot of expenditure. Transformers are occasionally loaded beyond nameplate ratings because of existing possible contingencies on the transmission lines, any failure or fault in power systems, or economic considerations. One of the reported damage or tripping of the distribution transformer is due to thermal overload. To eliminate the damaging of transformers due to overloading from consumer end, it involves the control against over current tripping of distribution transformer. Rise in operating temperature of the transformer due to overloading has an influence on ageing of transformers. The accelerated aging is one of the main consequences of overloading power transformers. Thus load limitations must be implemented to operate the transformers within safe limits. Moreover on overloading the transformers voltage regulation may increase and power factor drops.

The project is all about protecting the transformer under overload condition. This can be done by connecting another transformer in parallel through a microcontroller and a relay which shares the excess load of the first transformer. The transformers are switched alternatively to avoid thermal overloading. Therefore, two transformers work efficiently under overload condition and damage can be prevented. If there is a further increase in load beyond the capacity of two transformers there will be a priority based load shedding of consumers which will provide un-interrupted power supply for the hospitals, industries etc.

1.2 OBJECTIVE

The main aim of the project is to protect the transformer under overload condition by sharing load with a standby transformer and to provide un-interrupted power supply to the consumers. The GSM sends messages to the concerned authority whenever the load is shared between the parallel transformers.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Energy is the basic necessity for the economic development of a country. Many function necessary to present-day living grind to halt when the supply of energy stops. It is practically impossible to estimate the actual magnitude of the role that energy has played in building up present-day civilization. In this modern world, the dependence on electricity is so much that it has become a part & parcel of our life. The demand for electricity is increasing everyday frequent power cuts is causing many worriment in various areas likes industries, hospitals and houses resulting in load increment hence overload. An alternate arrangement for power is must. This project uses parallel transformers for load sharing at highest load on first transformer then automatically load transfer on to the second transformer. Thus load sharing in transformers, which was earlier done manually, is controlled and automated by a microcontroller based system. This project focuses on providing a secured environment for the

transformers from overloads which are distributing power to certain regions and also serves as a sustained power supply. Our project presents a reasonable microcontroller based automatic load sharing in transformers. A number of literatures related to the topic of control systems and automation were reviewed and analyzed.

2.1 Rekha.T, BinduPrakash, Asna.S, Dinesh. S and Nandana. S.Prasad (2015): Distribution transformers are an important part of power system which distributes power to the low-voltage users directly, and its operation condition is important for the entire distribution network operation. However, their life is significantly reduced if they are subjected to overloading and over temperature resulting in unexpected failures and loss of supply to a large number of customers thus effecting system reliability. Protection against fault in power systems is very essential and vital for its reliable performance. This project is a simplified approach to protect the transformers from unusual conditions. For this purpose two similar types of distribution transformers are used so that, if any one transformer fails, then immediately another transformer is brought into the circuit during over loading, over temperatures, input voltage variations and provides conventional 230V supply to the consumers without burning of transformers. Most of the loads (e.g. Induction motors, arc lamps) are inductive in nature and hence have low lagging power factor. The low power factor is highly undesirable as it causes an increase in current, resulting in additional losses of active power in all the elements of power system from power station generator down to the utilization devices. So in this paper an automatic power factor correction circuit is also incorporated with the load sharing module.

2.1 Ashish R. Ambalkar, Nitesh M. Bhojar, Vivek V. Badarkhe and Vivek B. Bathe (2015) : The transformer is very costly and bulky equipment of power system. It operates for 24 hours of a day and feeds the load. Sometimes the situation may occur when the load on the transformer is suddenly increased above its rated capacity. When this situation occurs, the transformer will be overloaded and overheated and damage the insulation of transformer resulting in interruption of supply. The best solution to avoid the overloading is to operate the number of transformers in parallel. In this work, a slave transformer shares the load of master transformer in the case of over load and over temperature. A sensor circuit is designed to log the data from master transformer and if it is found to be in overload condition, immediately the slave transformer will be connected in the parallel to the master transformer and the load is shared. Initially when we switched ON the load that load will be shared by the first transformer. Once load has been increased on first transformer above its rated capacity then the stand by transformer (second) will share the load automatically. . In this work we are used a relay and comparator IC's for automatic load sharing between three transformers. The number of transformers to be operated in parallel can also be increased according to demand of a particular area.

2.3 S.R.Balan, P.Sivanesan, R.Ramprakash, B.Ananthakannan and K.MithinSubash (2014) : Controlling of electric power substation equipments plays an important role in daily maintenance of electric power system. In an extra high voltage substation, the reliability required from substation components is critical. Applications of

controlling base station with the help of mobile of substation equipments could improve the quality of accelerating the process of any substation. The aim of this project is designed to control substation load shedding and sharing using a programmable switching control by automatically. In this project we demonstrate the working of this simple operation using a Microcontroller. The development of this application requires the configuration of the program through GSM module. In substation, there are many tasks like certain loads need to be switched on/off in specific time intervals. In this, the loads can be operated in three modes: Set mode, Auto mode and Manual mode. In set mode, through timers, the operation is based on input time set by the user whereas in auto mode it works on default time settings and finally in the manual mode it functions while respective loads are operated depending on the load necessity using GSM. All the modes and status of loads are displayed on an LCD. Finally GSM modem which send sms to the control system. We can select the mode and timing remotely.

3. PARALLEL OPERATION OF TRANSFORMERS

3.1 INTRODUCTION

- For supplying a load in excess of the rating of an existing transformer, two or more transformers may be connected in parallel with the existing transformer. The transformers are connected in parallel when load on one of the transformers is more than its capacity. The reliability is increased with parallel operation than to have single larger unit. The cost associated with maintaining the spares is less when two transformers are connected in parallel.
- It is usually economical to install another transformer in parallel instead of replacing the existing transformer by a single larger unit. The cost of a spare unit in the case of two parallel transformers (of equal rating) is also lower than that of a single large transformer. In addition, it is preferable to have a parallel transformer for the reason of reliability. With this at least half the load can be supplied with one transformer out of service.

3.2 CONDITIONS FOR PARALLELLING

- For parallel connection of transformers, primary windings of the Transformers are connected to source bus-bars and secondary windings are connected to the load bus-bars.
- Various conditions that must be fulfilled for the successful parallel operation of transformers:
 1. Same voltage Ratio & Turns Ratio (both primary and secondary Voltage Rating is same).
 2. Same Percentage Impedance and X/R ratio.
 3. Identical Position of Tap changer.
 4. Same KVA ratings.
 5. Same Phase angle shift (vector group are same).
 6. Same Frequency rating.

7. Same Polarity.
 8. Same Phase sequence.
- Some of these conditions are convenient and some are mandatory.
 - The convenient are: Same voltage Ratio & Turns Ratio, Same Percentage Impedance, Same KVA Rating, Same Position of Tap changer.
 - The mandatory conditions are: Same Phase Angle Shift, Same Polarity, Same Phase Sequence and Same Frequency.
 - When the convenient conditions are not met paralleled operation is possible but not optimal.

4. PROPOSED DESIGN AND DESCRIPTION

4.1 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

This project works on the principle of parallel operation of transformers. The system consists of microcontroller, transformers, circuit breakers, relay, Current Transformer (CT), GSM modem and LCD display. The transformers are step down transformers in which only one transformer is operating under normal condition. The input to the transformer is fed through a circuit breaker to which a relay is connected. The circuit breaker is in closed position for transformer which is operating. Here the transformer feeds five loads which are provided with individual circuit breakers for protection. A standby transformer is connected in parallel to the main transformer through a circuit breaker. In order to measure the current through the transformer a current transformer is connected to the secondary of the operating transformer. The current transformer measures the load current continuously and is fed to the microcontroller through a rectifier circuit. The output from the current transformer can also be fed directly to inbuilt ADC pins of controller, instead of using a rectifier. A GSM connected to the controller enables communication between the system and control room. The maximum load limit is entered to the controller through a keypad and a LCD display gives an indication of the same. The microcontroller continuously compares the CT value with the maximum limit entered. Whenever the current exceeds the maximum limit, the main transformer gets overloaded and the second transformer shares the total load equally. At the same time the GSM sends a message to the control room. When there is a further increase in load beyond the rated capacity of two transformers, microcontroller will give control signal to the circuit breaker of respective load to open, based on the priority level set by the user. When the load decreases and comes to normal value which is less than the maximum limit, the first transformer will shut down automatically. This type of alternative switching method avoids the possibility of thermal overloading by providing enough time for the transformer to cool naturally. Each time the transformer is overloaded or switched a message is sent to the control room about the mode of operation. Thus it enables efficient operation of existing transformer and provides un-interrupted power supply to hospitals, industries and other important areas.

4.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

The Project is designed with the Microcontroller ATMEGA328P. The heat parameters and current parameters are fed as base values, using a keypad to the Microcontroller and the output signal are provided to operate a relay by comparing the base values with the operating parameters. The application consists of a board of electronic components inclusive of a Microcontroller. It has been designed to work with high accuracy. The heat parameters of the power transformer are sensed by temperature sensor IC LM35 and current parameters by current transformer. By comparing the values the Microcontroller produces a trip signal which operates the relay and in turn the affinity between main transformer and parallel transformer is started and capacity is shared, thus protecting the power transformer from malfunctioning. The output shall be observed the current condition, as to which source supplies the load is also exhibit on a liquid crystal diode (LCD). The global system for mobile (GSM) communication is used as it is accepted standard for digital communication and is helpful in sending message to authority via SMS whenever load is shared between the parallel transformers.

4.3 BLOCK DIAGRAM

The block diagram gives a brief idea about various important parts of our project. Here the important parts are circuit breaker, Transformers, microcontroller, relay, Current Transformer, GSM modem.

FIG 4.3 BLOCK DIAGRAM

4.4 CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

FIG 4.4 CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

The circuit diagram of the proposed system is shown in figure 5.1. Here two transformers share 5 loads which can be controlled independently.

4.5 CIRCUIT DIAGRAM DESCRIPTION

The circuit diagram consists of two transformers of which only one transformer is working under normal load condition. Each transformer is connected with a relay and the loads are connected to the secondary coil of the transformer. Transformers work only when the relays are latched. The transformer used here is step down transformer which converts 230V to 12V. The controller and LCD require a DC operating voltage of 5V while the relay and GSM operate at a DC voltage ranging from 9V to 12V. A power supply circuit is provided to get 12V and 5V DC from the 230V mains by a full wave bridge rectifier. A 7805 regulator ensures a regulated 5V supply to the LCD and controller. Here five inductive loads are connected to the transformer each provided with an individual relay. A current transformer continuously measures the load current of the transformer and feeds to the controller. The current transformer is connected to a zener diode in order to measure quick response. Under normal working condition relay 1 is latched and supply passes to the load through a manual switch and a relay contact. Normally the relay will be latched initially and on receiving a low signal from microcontroller the relay will be de-energized and becomes open thus interrupting the supply. The controller is programmed in such a way to send a low signal to relay when the transformers are overloaded. Thus the load cannot be operated even if the manual switch is closed. At the

same time the GSM sends a message to the control room about the transformer operation. Here as the fifth load is switched on both the transformers are overloaded and in order to maintain the supply priority based load shedding is also included.

Whenever the load decreases and reaches a normal level, transformers are switched alternatively to avoid thermal overloading. The main advantage of this type of switching is that, it allows the transformer to cool by natural methods thus increasing its lifespan.

5. ADVANTAGES

- 1) Automatic load sharing by transformers.
- 2) No manual errors are taking place.
- 3) It prevents the main transformer from damage due to the problems like overload and overheats.
- 4) Un-interrupted power supply to the consumers is supplied.
- 5) Complete monitoring of transformers.
- 6) SMS alert to concerned authority by GSM technique.

6. CONCLUSION

In this project we observed that if load on one transformer is increases then the relay will sense the change in current & microcontroller operates & slave transformers comes automatically in operation to share the load.

The work on “Automatic load sharing of transformers” is successfully designed, tested and a demo unit is fabricated for operating three transformers in parallel to share the load automatically with the help of change over relay and relay driver circuit and also to protect the transformers from overloading and thus providing an uninterrupted power supply to the customers.

7. REFERENCE

- [1] Dr.J.B.V.Subrahmanyam,T.C.Subramanyam,T.C.Srinivasarao,M.Kalavani and HarithaInavolu, “Auto Control of a Standby Transformer Using Microcontroller”, International Journal of Advances In Engineering Research, Vol. 2, Issue 5, pp. 1199-1204, 2011.
- [2] S.R.Balan, P.Sivanesan, R.Ramprakash, B.Ananthakannan and K.MithinSubash, “GSM Based Automatic Substation LoadShedding and Sharing Using Programmable Switching Control”, Journal of Selected Areas in Microelectronics, Volume 6, Issue 2, pp. 59-61, 2014.
- [3] Ashish R. Ambalkar, Nitesh M. Bhojar, Vivek V. Badarkhe and Vivek B. Bathe, “Automatic Load Sharing of Transformers”, International Journal for Scientific Research & Development, Volume 2, Issue 12, pp. 739-741,2015.
- [4] Rekha.T, BinduPrakash, Asna. S, Dinesh.S and Nandana.S.Prasad, “An Intelligent Method for Load Sharing of Transformers With Temperature Monitoring and Automatic Correction of Power Factor”, International Journal Of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology, Volume 4, Issue3, pp. 416-421, 2015.